

Analyzing the Existence of AI Threats That Could Reduce Human Employment Opportunities and Job Replacement in the Future

TABLE I. VARIABLES AND INDICATORS

Code	Question	Ref
Personal wellbeing concern		
PWC1	AI makes me feel relaxed.	[1] [3] [5]
PWC2	AI makes me feel anxious.	
PWC3	AI makes me feel redundant.	
PWC4	AI makes me feel useless.	
PWC5	AI makes me feel inferior.	
PWC6	AI increases my job.	
Perceived severity		
PSEV1	AI may perpetuate cultural stereotypes in available data.	[1] [8] [9]
PSEV2	AI may amplify discrimination in available data.	
PSEV3	AI may be prone to reproducing institutional biases in available data.	
PSEV4	AI may have a propensity for intensifying systemic bias in available data.	
PSEV5	AI may have the wrong objective due to the difficulty of specifying the objective explicitly.	
PSEV6	AI may use inadequate structures such as problematic models.	
PSEV7	AI may perform poorly due to insufficient training.	
Perceived Threat		
PT1	My fear of exposure to AI's risks is high.	[1]
PT2	The extent of my worry about AI's risks is low.	[4]
PT3	My concerns about the potential for errors or negative impacts from using AI are very high.	[6]
AI identity		
AID1	Thinking about myself in relation to AI, I feel enthusiastic.	[2] [7] [1]
AID2	Thinking about myself in relation to AI, I feel pumped up.	
AID3	Thinking about myself in relation to AI, I feel energized.	
AID4	Thinking about myself in relation to AI, I feel confident.	
AID5	Thinking about myself in relation to AI, I am close to AI.	
Loss of status position		
LSP1	The introduction of a AI will reduce my competences.	[2] [10]] [11]]
LSP2	I think that my position will be less important with the introduction of AI.	
LSP3	I think that after the introduction of AI, I can no longer decide everything on my own.	
LSP4	After the introduction of AI, in the future only the system decides.	
LSP5	By the introduction of AI, I am limited in my possibilities.	
Threat to job security		
TJS1	I am worried about having to leave my job before I would like to.	[2]
TJS2	There is a risk that I will have to leave my present job in the year to come.	[9] [7]
TJS3	I feel uneasy about losing my job in the near future.	
Loss of skills/expertise		

LSE1	I fear that when using AI, employees may lose their expert status.	[2] [1] [3]
LSE2	I fear that when using AI, specialized work-related skills will not be needed anymore.	
LSE3	I fear that when using AI, certain specializations can be replaced.	
LSE4	I fear that when using AI, employees may feel less competent.	
AI identity threat		
AIT1	If I use AI, people in my group will not support me.	[2] [5] [6]
AIT2	Using AI makes me feel not respected by others in my group.	
AIT3	Using AI makes me feel not confident that I understand it well enough to get the job done.	
AIT4	Using AI makes me feel like I have less abilities to get the job done.	
Job replacement		
JR1	I am afraid that an AI technique/product may make us dependent	[3] [7] [4]
JR2	I am afraid that an AI technique/product may make us even lazier.	
JR3	I am afraid that an AI technique/product may replace humans.	
JR4	I am afraid that widespread use of AI will take jobs away from people.	
JR5	I am afraid that if I begin to use AI techniques/products I will become dependent upon them and lose some of my reasoning skills.	
JR6	I am afraid that AI techniques/products will replace someone's job.	